

0.5 mg indole acetic acid/liter, and 1 mg 2,4-D/liter while ER had 0.11 mg zeatin/liter, 2 mg 2,4-D/liter, and 0.07 mg picloram/liter.

Heat treatment increased callus induction efficiency in both media (see table). At 0 and 5 min, ER induced higher efficiencies than E10. At 15 min, however, there was a dramatic increase using E10 media. Cold shock, which has been a part of the standard operational

procedure in anther culture in most cereals, promotes the synchrony and viability of the pollen grains and may activate some enzymes which are necessary in callus production. On the other hand, heat treatment has been popular in *Brassica* genus. This study demonstrates that heat treatment before cold shock could increase callus production in IR42. In the same manner as in cold shock, heat may, aside from

promoting synchrony and viability, activate enzymes necessary to induce the pollen grains toward vegetative development (in this case, callus production) instead of their normal generative function.

Some of the calli produced have been transferred to plant regeneration medium to determine the plant regeneration efficiency after heat treatment. *J*

Pest Control and Management DISEASES

Seedling age in relation to sheath rot (ShR) occurrence in rice

B.N. Singh, S.P. Sahu, Y. Prasad, and R.S. Singh, Rajendra Agricultural University, Pusa (Samastipur), Bihar 648125, India

ShR caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* is

becoming an important disease in rainfed lowland rice, especially in delayed plantings. In 1984 wet season, ShR occurrence was observed in a replicated yield trial comprising 32 entries. Seedlings (25- and 50-d-old) were transplanted in 3 replications in 11-m² plots; 60 kg N/ha, 18 kg P/ha, and

17 kg K/ha were applied. N was used in 4 splits: 1/4 basal and the remaining as topdressing in 3 splits. Scoring followed the 1980 *Standard evaluation system for rice* at harvest under natural infection. The maximum score over three replications was recorded to avoid escapes.

ShR occurrence was high in 50-d-old seedlings. TCA72, TCA48, and TCA227 were highly resistant at both ages. CR1002, Jaishree, IR4819-17-3-2, and IET7591, which were resistant at 25 d were susceptible to highly susceptible when transplanted at 50 d (see table). TCA190-1, TCA148-3, TCA225, IR4570-74-2-2-3-3, RAU73-76-140-1, BR8, BR34, Janaki, and IET6286 were resistant to moderately resistant at both ages. In general, photoperiod-sensitive tall varieties were more resistant than photoperiod-insensitive ones. The mean score was 2.9 for 25d-old seedlings and 5.7 for 50-d-old. *J*

ShR score and other characters of 32 varieties.

Variety	ShR score ^a		Av days to 50% flowering	Photoperiod sensitivity ^b	Plant height ^c
	25 d	50 d			
RAUSBS80-565	1	5	124	S	9
RAUSBS 80-566	3	5	124	S	9
RAUSBS 80-571	1	5	121	S	9
TCA190-1	1	3	132	S	9
TCA72	1	1	115	S	9
TCA148-3	1	3	115	S	9
TCA80-4	1	5	115	I	5
TCA48	1	1	115	S	9
TCA225	1	3	122	S	9
TCA227	1	1	125	S	9
RAUSBS 80-585	5	9	124	S	9
RP1491-24	5	9	122	I	1
RAU83-18-8	1	5	116	I	1
R114-2-1-1-1	9	9	128	I	1
IR4570-74-2-2-3-3	1	5	108	I	1
MTU7029 (Swarna)	7	9	122	I	1
RAU73-16-1-40-1	1	3	112	I	1
CR1002	1	9	119	I	1
RAU83-8-4	5	5	111	I	1
Pankaj	5	9	121	I	1
BR8	1	3	117	S	9
Jaishree	1	9	120	I	9
Mahsuri	3	5	115	I	9
Radha	5	9	115	I	5
BR34	3	3	108	S	9
Janki (64-117)	1	3	114	S	9
IR4819-17-3-2	3	9	112	I	1
CR1009 (Savitri)	9	9	102	I	1
ET759 1	1	7	123	I	1
IET6286	1	3	115	I	5
IR13146-45-2-3	7	9	115	I	1
RP975-109-2	5	9	120	I	1
Mean	2.9	5.7			

^aBy SES. ^bS = photoperiod sensitive, I = photoperiod insensitive. ^c1 = semidwarf, 5 = intermediate, 9 = tall.

Rice grassy stunt (GSV) and rice ragged stunt (RSV) carriers

Z.M. Flores, H. Hibino, and J. Perfect, Entomology Department, IRRI

ELISA tests on brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* collected daily in a high-beam light trap on the top of a three-floor building at IRRI were conducted to identify GSV and RSV carriers. The light trap was designed to catch migrating BPH.

Individual BPH were homogenized with 0.50 ml-0.02 M phosphate buffer